

Map of available support services and programmes in each EU28 country

D5.1 version 1.5

October 2018

merlin

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Executive summary

This document, D5.1 — Map of available support services and programmes in each EU28 country – is a deliverable of the MERLIN project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement #780460, and has been prepared by taking into account the template of the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020" and the "Fact Sheet: Open Access in Horizon 2020".

Merlin aims to foster and accelerate the transfer of knowledge from the projects funded in FP7 and H2020, be it on the form of license agreement, patent or ideally, spinoff or startup to directly exploit them, by organising practical hands-on workshops; meet ups with potential partners, customers and investors; and by attending scientific conferences to reach a wider public. The programme will equip participants with knowledge, skills and a network to generate market-led business models to unlock potential and accelerate this journey.

The purpose of this deliverable is to describe the creation and design of an online tool that will help people identify suitable participant programmes, either public or private, which can fill in their needs of funding or finding partners, given the current status of their research results. This status is gathered through a questionnaire comprising six questions, also developed in the context of Work Package 5 as a result of the interviews carried out.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable (D5.1), “*Map of available support services and programmes in each EU28 country*”, is a deliverable of the MERLIN project, which is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 under Grant Agreement #780460 and has been prepared by taking into account the template of the "Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020"¹ and the "Fact Sheet: Open Access in Horizon 2020"².

Funding in ICT project under FP7 and H2020 totals over 11.000 million € by the end of the current work programme. Stimulated and supported by these programs, many researchers in universities, institutes and SMEs have worked hard on developing new ground-breaking technologies and disruptive services. But when it comes to commercialize the results or create a company, these researchers are unsure on how to proceed. MERLIN project, funded in the context of the EC initiative *Innovation Radar*, wants to start changing this situation by organizing a set of activities aiming:

- To stimulate a greater interest in the scientific community to view their research results as potential opportunities to be exploited with the correct business model.
- To equip researchers with modern, need-first and market-led methodologies that will help them to shape their ideas and outputs into innovations to be ready for market validation and posterior commercialization.
- To introduce the rich European entrepreneurship ecosystem and the opportunities it offers to create and support startups on their journey.

Among the planned activities, it is worth highlighting the following:

- Organisation of 45 practical workshops covering state-of-the-art innovation and entrepreneurship methodologies in 8 European cities.
- Organisation of 5 workshops in scientific conferences to reach more researchers and engage them with the activities organized by MERLIN and other ICT-32 projects.
- Organisation of 8 meet ups with potential partners, customers and investors by the end of each year.
- Organisation of 4 webinars on SME growth and new business models for public-private partnership.

The purpose of D5.1 is to describe the design and creation of an online tool for helping innovators find suitable programmes in any of the EU countries, which can help them with their needs regarding funding, finding partners, or other issues. For the identification of the current status of the user, we previously developed a questionnaire to evaluate him/her in six axes: Idea Stage, Technology Maturity, Market maturity, Financials, Amount, and Team. With these questions, the tool identifies the current status of the user, and then recommends some programmes based on the matching between the current status of the person and the expectations of the programme, since it doesn't make sense to recommend a scale-up programme to an early stage startup or vice-versa. The database of programmes and opportunities will be completed by all members of the Consortium.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

² https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/sites/horizon2020/files/FactSheet_Open_Access.pdf

The tool is hosted in a subdomain of the project website: <https://growthradar.merlin-ict.eu> and it is available to the general public. By the time this deliverable was published (November 2018), its database stored programmes from Ireland and Spain mainly, since these two countries were chosen for the first version of the tool. But all the partners of MERLIN consortium will complete the database with the programmes available on their countries and countries nearby during the project lifecycle. Also, any errors found in the database or in the tool itself will be corrected.

1.1. Audience

The main intended audience for this document is the MERLIN project consortium and the European Commission. But its main result, the online tool hosted on the project website, is meant to be used by anyone who is searching for programmes that could help him/her find new funding opportunities, programmes specifically designed to find new partners, or has other needs.

1.2. Structure

The structure of the document is as follows:

- Section 2 describes the creation of the Participant Background Questionnaire, a questionnaire developed to assess the current status of the innovators regarding their business idea. This questionnaire is filled in by the participants of the workshops and is also employed in the online tool for suggesting supporting programmes to users.
- Section 3 describes the application of Software Engineering principles to the design of the online application and shows some of the diagrams supporting the requirements elicitation step, software architecture and graphical user interface modelling.
- Section 4 shows the detailed implementation of the first version of the tool. It motivates the selection of the implementation framework (Angular in this case) and shows some screenshots of the tool.
- Section 5 summarizes the conclusions and outlines future improvements to the tool.

2. Design of the Evaluation Questionnaire

Each participant in the MERLIN workshops across the various delivery sites is provided with a participant background questionnaire. The purpose of this questionnaire is to identify at what stage the participant is at in the innovation journey from initial idea to market introduction as well as capturing what type of support services they are most interested in.

The questionnaire was divided into three main sections:

- Personal information
 - Contact details
 - Type of organization
 - Role
- Innovation stage
 - Idea
 - Market
 - Financial (including amount raised)
 - Team
- Support services
 - Financial
 - Partners
 - Other

The data is collected by the partners and reported to a central repository on excel for easy comparison. A brief analysis of initial results is provided below in Section 2.3. Some minor edits to the questionnaire have been made based on feedback from facilitators in the initial workshops, however the main structure of the innovation stage has remained the same thus far.

2.1. Interviews with stakeholders

As part of the initial activities, we conducted interviews with experts who would understand the journey and challenges that researchers go through when trying to commercialise their research or make their spin-off or start-up grow. The aim of these interviews was to identify the different needs and actions that different profiles of researchers have at the various stages along their journey and what type of services are appropriate and effective in supporting their success.

The results of these interviews were used to inform the actions of the MERLIN project and aid the identification promising researchers and pertinent actions. Each interview was conducted through either GoToMeeting or by phone and lasted for 45-60 minutes.

2.1.1 Participants

We interviewed four people in total from three of the partner countries. Partners contacted several people, and finally we selected four from different organizations and backgrounds, so that we could have the widest

spectrum possible to take into account as many points of view as possible. The details of the persons contacted are shown in the following table:

Ecosystem	Type	Subject	Date
Spain	Support Programme Organiser - Technology Transfer	BL	14 th March 2018
Poland	Entrepreneur	MS	7 th February 2018
UK	Support Programme Organiser	MP	7 th February 2018
	Support Programme Organiser/Entrepreneur	HJ	13 th February 2018

2.1.2 Interview Questionnaire

Based on the previous experience of the project partners, we designed a questionnaire for the interview, which was created and enhanced on two monthly telcos. The questionnaire comprised three sections: questions about the interviewee background; questions about why he/she thinks researchers do not exploit, in general, their research results; and questions about the kind of services researchers would require in order to start exploiting them. The questionnaire is shown in the following table:

BACKGROUND
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What best describes you? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Support programme organiser/instructor ▪ Researcher who has transitioned to a successful SME/spin-off ▪ Previous mentor to researchers ▪ Current researcher ○ Are you performing current activities related to the MERLIN project? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Yes/No ○ If so, could you briefly describe them.
MARKET-FOCUSED RESEARCHERS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ In your opinion are there different categories of researchers who have set-up or wish to set-up a business? E.g. early-stage post-doctoral researcher or late-stage senior lecturer. ○ What are the key challenges that researchers face in the journey from academic to entrepreneur and company director? ○ Which of those challenges are the greatest? i.e. what are the top 3 priorities? ○ Are those challenges specific to any of the categories mentioned previously?

SERVICES

- What are the top 5 needs that a researcher has when trying to transition from academic to a company forming role?
- What type of services are required to meet those needs?
- From your experience in currently provided services, what services have had the most impact on supporting researchers in making the shift?
- Thinking of researchers that have established a business and are looking for the best way to grow. What are their specific needs? Do they differ from the previous stage?
- What types of services are most useful for this group?
- Who were the interviewees and how were the interviews (questions, length, etc.). A table comparing the answers maybe and some conclusions

2.1.3 Interview highlights

The following table summarises some of the key outcomes and insights from the interviews, which have contributed to the definition of the six criteria and have had some impact on the project approach.

Interview summary	
Definition of the researcher turned entrepreneur	<p>The profile of the researcher who attempts the commercialisation journey and/or spin-off varies greatly from recent PhD graduates to experienced PIs looking to prepare for their retirement. The researchers are more driven by pull factors rather than by push, i.e. they believe in their technologies and want to see them reach the market and they see an opportunity. Another profile mentioned, is the PI who wishes to create an opportunity for their students as well as having another vehicle to hire researchers and finish off projects.</p> <p>An advantage that the researcher turned entrepreneur has is the wider knowledge of technological advances in their area and thus a greater understanding of the freedom to operate.</p> <p>Within these profiles there can be two types of innovator – the inventor and the adaptor where the former is less risk adverse and is more driven by personal challenges leading to more transformative products.</p>
Key challenges	<p>Some of the key challenges are context specific, e.g. in Spain, participation in a spin-off by a public researcher is limited and represents a barrier while in other regions, certain universities provide sabbaticals of up to 3 years to enable the researcher to dedicate themselves wholly to the innovation journey.</p> <p>Researchers across the three countries do appear to face similar challenges:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Network 2. Skills 3. Financing

	<p>Researchers, by the nature of the sector and their training, tend to have closed networks limited to other researchers in their field and need to invest in growing their business networks and gaining access to wider range of people who can help them either as business partners or collaborators.</p> <p>The researcher's skills lend themselves well to the development of projects and new technologies but often in the context of commercialisation means they obsess on technology or solution rather than the problem. In addition, researchers can find the move to the more commercial or even administrative aspects of a business is too much of a leap and require someone with the commercial skills and experience to enter as CEO.</p> <p>Another aspect is finding the right team, often spin-outs are based on high technologies or 'deeptech' and this presents the challenge of finding the talent with the right skills to develop it further including the financing to be able to hire them.</p> <p>In terms of financing, during the early stages it can be difficult for all companies starting off, but for researchers there is often some small grants available either from within their organisation or public bodies. Researchers need to be mindful that they don't spend too much time on grants rather than finance for growth.</p>
Key needs	<p>Mentoring/tutoring</p> <p>Role models</p> <p>Exposure to the entrepreneurial ecosystem and mindset</p> <p>Exposure to customers</p> <p>Talent and partners</p> <p>Finance (not just grants)</p>
Relevant support Services	<p>The primary services suggested includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to institutional equipment and machinery at a low cost during initial development • Supporting finding business partners • Training in establishing a company and finding investment • Introductions to investors • Public grants • Export and manufacturing advice • Legal support • Pitching competitions • Mentoring programmes

2.2. Design of the participant background questionnaire

From the results of the interviews, carried out from February to March 2018, we developed the “*Participant Background Questionnaire*” (PBQ). This questionnaire was designed to be simple to complete and able to

capture the relevant data on participants. Through a combination of six questions with a Likert-scale for the answers, a unique profile of each participant would be built based on their stage of the innovation journey.

While the Innovation Radar methodology prepared by the JRC aims to be comprehensive and objective with a focus on the innovation and the external market potential³, this questionnaire aims to focus on the individual and the current maturity of their idea, market development and financial status. This permits a subjective assessment that will enable the self-selection of the most appropriate services for them and enable the MERLIN team to identify high-potential researchers or entrepreneurs to provide with further opportunities (meet-ups, conferences, etc.).

With this dual purpose in mind, potential opportunities for finance, incubation programmes and other common methods for supporting technological innovation were researched for their application criteria. This information was complimented by the outcomes of the interviews with experts, extensive experience of the consortium in supporting researchers and entrepreneurs as well as previous work in this area.⁴

This resulted in the definition of six key parameters; Idea, Technology, Market, Financials, Amount, Team. The definition of each stage of maturity borrows from established methodologies where relevant and from the experience of the consortium. For example, the idea maturity and market development mirrors the process present in the Customer Discovery methodology⁵ and the technology maturity is a compression of the Technology Readiness Levels as defined by the European Commission in the H2020 Work Programme 2016-2017.⁶ The exact definitions have evolved as an iterative process between partners and in response to use in workshops.

The following table describes the classification of each parameter on the Likert-scale, from 1 to 5, where 1 represents the first step in the process and 5 market launch. While the questionnaire may be limited as presenting the journey from idea to successful market introduction as a linear process, it is believed that it is representative of the generic stages for each ecosystem and is thus globally applicable and scalable.

N°	Idea	Technology	Market	Finance	Amount	Team
1	I have ideas that I believe to have commercial potential	Technology has been validated in a lab environment - basic components	I have a general idea of relevant sectors/markets	I am exploring how to fund development	€0-10,000	I am currently working on my own
2	I have an idea for the commercial-	Technology has been validated in a	I have a clearly defined market	I have received initial funding	€10-35,000	I have general co-

³ De Prato, G., Nepelski, D. and Piroli, G. (2015). Innovation Radar: Identifying Innovations and Innovators with High Potential in ICT FP7, CIP & H2020 Projects. JRC Scientific and Policy Reports – EUR 27314 EN. Seville: JRC-IPTS

⁴ <https://infogram.com/global-tech-accelerators-1g6v4m761qro218>

⁵ Blank, S. (2013). The four steps to the epiphany: successful strategies for products that win. BookBaby.

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/wp/2016_2017/annexes/h2020-wp1617-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

	isation of my results	relevant environment - model system		from my organisation		developers/co-founders
3	I have developed potential Business Model(s)	Technology has been demonstrate-ed in a relevant environment - prototype system	I have clearly defined market segments and potential customers	I have received initial external funding to develop the idea (private/public)	€35-50,000	I have developers/co-founders and an initial team of employees
4	I am actively exploring the potential business models	System prototype demonstrate-ed in a operational environment - beta test	I have engaged with potential customers and received inputs	I have received initial investment to develop a prototype	€50-100,000	I have co-founders and an initial team of employees (<5)
5	I have a proven business model and am focusing on getting to market	System complete and qualified - ready to ship	I have developed pilots or trials with potential customers	I have received investment to reach the market	€ >100,000	I have co-founders and a team of employees (>5)

The suggested list of potential services was developed through combining the feedback provided in interviews and desk research and was split into 3 sections – financial, partners, other, as shown in the following table:

Financial	Partners	Other
Public funding to develop innovation further	Potential co-founders	Support in developing a successful business model
Public funding to reach market	Technology development partners	Support developing a go-to-market strategy
Public funding to grow markets	Market development partners	Introductions to potential clients
Low-interest business loans	Technology platform partners	Intellectual property advice
Tailored bank-loans	Distribution partners	Access to specialist equipment
Angel investment (<€100,000)	Corporate piloting partners	Access to workspace
Seed investment (<€500,000)	Incubation/acceleration programmes	Other (please write)

2.3. Initial results of participant background questionnaire

At the date of this report, there have been 185 individual data entries (excluding repeat participants) collected across 5 cities and 2 conferences (7 MERLIN workshops in total). The results of this preliminary analysis are already showing interesting trends across geographies and will help prioritise the collection of services for the growth tool. Below we briefly describe some of the highlights with complete tables available in Annex 1 of this document.

2.3.1 Innovation maturity

Comparing the average values from the workshops conducted in the different cities and conferences, there is a difference observed between the participants. In general, as can be observed from the table below, the Warsaw participants are the most progressed across all indicators while Madrid and the conferences are the least progressed. Vilnius and Warsaw are the cohorts with the most advanced ideas and tech while those Poznan, Vilnius and Warsaw believe themselves to be most advanced in terms of market.

City/Event	Idea Stage	Technology Maturity	Market	Financials	Amount Received	Team Details
Cambridge	2,5	2,1	2,4	1,7	1,8	2,3
ECSA	2,3	1,3	1,5	2,3	0,5	2,3
IoT Week	1,0	2,0	1,5	2,0	1,0	1,0
Madrid	1,8	1,5	1,7	1,6	1,5	2,0
Poznan	2,6	2,0	2,8	1,3	0,7	2,4
Vilnius	2,6	3,2	2,6	2,0	2,9	2,2
Warsaw	3,5	3,0	3,1	2,4	2,1	3,4
TOTAL	2,6	2,4	2,5	1,8	1,9	2,4

Comparing the different results obtained by workshop shows little variation, participants in the Business Model Canvas workshop were more likely to be at an earlier phase while the other workshops appear close to the global average, with exception to the conferences.

Average per Workshop	Idea Stage	Technology Maturity	Market	Financials	Amount Received	Team Details
BMC	2,4	2,4	2,5	1,4	2,0	2,2
CDIS	2,8	2,5	2,6	2,1	1,8	2,7
CONF	1,8	1,5	1,5	2,2	0,7	1,8

LSM	2,6	2,2	2,4	1,8	1,9	2,5
Total	2,6	2,4	2,5	1,8	1,9	2,4

2.3.2 Key services

Across all services, the most popular is public funding for innovation development followed by support in developing a successful business model. This varies across cities with participants, e.g. Cambridge more likely to value support in meeting clients than public funding in Poznan, Madrid and Warsaw. With consequence for the EFSI and ESIF actions related to stimulating investment in innovation, only 3% and 9% are interested in tailored bank loans or low interest loans respectively.

Top Services	1	2	3	=	=
CAMBRIDGE	Introductions to potential clients	Support in developing a successful business model	Support developing a go-to-market strategy		
MADRID	Public Funding to develop innovation further	Technology development partners	Support in developing a successful business model		
POZNAN	Public Funding to develop innovation further	Technology development partners	Technology platform partners	Support in developing a successful business model	Support developing a go-to-market strategy
VILNIUS	Support in developing a successful business model	Incubation/acceleration programmes	Technology development partners		
WARSAW	Public Funding to develop innovation further	Introductions to potential clients	Disribution partners		

The full results of the comparison of all services in the questionnaire and by level of maturity in each category can be found in the Annex to this deliverable.

3. Design of the Online Tool

This section describes the design of the MERLIN online tool for suggesting supporting programmes in three main fields (financial support, search for partners, other needs) to users of the tool, from those who have an incipient idea to those who have already created the company and are selling their product. The design has been carried out by following well-known Software Engineering⁷ methodologies and practices, which are enumerated in the first subsection. Then we describe functional and non-functional requirements for the application, use cases, and the relationship between both. The section continues with the description of the typical client-server architecture selected for the web application, and ends with the modelling of the graphical interface and the navigation scheme.

3.1. Methodology

The methodology used to generate the requirements specification document and the design of the architecture and components follows a set of steps as outlined below:

- Description of the list of functional and non-functional requirements of the online tool, as well as business goals and constraints.
- Definition of the use cases needed to obtain the stakeholders and final functionalities of the online tool.
- Matching of the requirements and the use cases identified.
- Definition of architectural design suitable to implement the previous requirements.
- Review the state of the art regarding the existing platforms, tools and solutions.
- Selection of the Web-based platforms and tools that best fit the previous requirements; and correspondences between the requirements and the functionality of the selected tool.
- Implementation of the tool in the selected platform/s.

3.2. Application Requirements

High-level requirements are the requirements operating mainly on the platform. We differentiate between two types of requirements: *functional* and *non-functional*. Functional requirements define the functions and behaviour of the application from the point of view of its observable behaviour, while non-functional requirements define the usability and user experience provided by it. Requirements are defined in the following subsections in a simple way, containing an ID, a description, a motivation, and a relevance rating, with values *Important*, *Desirable*, *Nice-to-Have*, and *Low Importance*.

⁷ Software Engineering. Ian Sommerville. Ed. Pearson, 2015

3.2.1 Functional requirements

Requirement identifier	FR-01
Requirement description	Users should be able to search for supporting programmes in European countries
Requirement motivation	Supporting programmes are normally available only at some countries, and user may want to establish or open a new business in other country
Relevance	Important

Requirement identifier	FR-02
Requirement description	Users should be able to select what kind of supporting programme they are looking for
Requirement motivation	There are different supporting programmes in Europe, making different offers and having different requirements
Relevance	Important

Requirement identifier	FR-03
Requirement description	Users should provide information about the current status of their innovation/product/service for better selecting programmes that fit their needs
Requirement motivation	This is needed in order to guide the filtering and sorting order of the search results, and find the most suitable programmes for the users
Relevance	Important

Requirement identifier	FR-04
Requirement description	The application should gather general information about the users in order to analyze the status of innovators in Europe
Requirement motivation	We need to gather some data about the users that can help us elaborate further statistics about them (showing aggregated data only)
Relevance	Nice to have

Requirement identifier	FR-05
Requirement description	Users should be able to propose new supporting programmes, so that project partners can add them to the database
Requirement motivation	Although partners will add new programmes to enrich the database, it is possible that they miss some. So, it is necessary to include a way to let users inform MERLIN partners about the existence of new programmes
Relevance	Nice to have

Requirement identifier	FR-06
Requirement description	Users should be able to select different sorting criteria for ordering the results of the search
Requirement motivation	In order to provide different sorting and results
Relevance	Nice to have

Requirement identifier	FR-07
Requirement description	The tool should present the results of the search, organized according to the suitability of the programmes given the status of the innovation/product/service provided by the user
Requirement motivation	So that users can then look for more details of programmes that are more appropriate for them
Relevance	Important

Requirement identifier	FR-08
Requirement description	The results of the search should be printed or stored in the user computer
Requirement motivation	So that the user can recover them
Relevance	Desirable

3.2.2 Non-Functional Requirements

Requirement identifier	NFR-01
Requirement description	Accessible
Requirement motivation	The online platform shall be accessible from different type of devices. At the same time, the system must be easy to use and compatible with web browsers. The system should be sufficiently fast to accommodate various Internet connection bandwidths. Many users have different kinds of devices and operating systems. A tool that has no dependencies on proprietary software will have a greater adoption
Relevance	Desirable

Requirement identifier	NFR-02
Requirement description	Available
Requirement motivation	The online platform shall be available 24 x 7 x 365
Relevance	Desirable

Requirement identifier	NFR-03
Requirement description	Secured and Restorable
Requirement motivation	The online platform shall provide a data backup facility for disaster recovery
Relevance	Important

Requirement identifier	NFR-04
Requirement description	Capacity and Scalability
Requirement motivation	The online platform shall provide data processing and concurrent user capacities
Relevance	Important

Requirement identifier	NFR-05
Requirement description	Performance
Requirement motivation	The online platform shall give acceptable speed of page loads and calculations. The system should be able to handle multiple transactions concurrently
Relevance	Desirable

Requirement identifier	NFR-06
Requirement description	Reliable
Requirement motivation	The online platform shall be consistent and offer dependable quality of service. The system shall survive communication breakdowns and failures, keeping the data available
Relevance	Important

Requirement identifier	NFR-07
Requirement description	Secure
Requirement motivation	The online platform shall guarantee the privacy of the personal data exchanged. The system must guarantee that customers' sensitive data is transmitted securely. The security of the system information shall be insured by means of the usual ICT technology
Relevance	Important

Requirement identifier	NFR-08
Requirement description	Useable
Requirement motivation	The online platform shall be easy to use by target users
Relevance	Important

3.3. Use Cases

Use cases⁸ emerged from the object-oriented software development world. They describe the software to be developed from the user point of view, highlighting the typical interactions between the users of a system and the system itself. The use cases considered for MERLIN online tool are shown in Figure 1. As can be seen in the figure, three main actors have been considered: users of the tool (innovators, start-ups, spinoffs), developers of the tool, and the database, as part of the system.

Figure 1. Use cases for the online application

The following tables describe each use case in more detail.

⁸ Use Case Modeling. Kurt Bittner. Ed. Addison-Wesley Professional, 2002.

Use Case	Search for 'Financial' programmes (UC1)
Description	The user wants to search for 'Financial' programmes in Europe that could help him/her improving the business/idea he/she is working on
Actors	User, Main Database
Assumptions	The user has evaluated himself or herself according to six criteria defined in the tool: Idea Stage, Technology Maturity, Market maturity, Financials, Amount, Team
Pre-conditions	The database has data from the country selected by the user
Post-conditions	The database stores new, anonymous information about the user: innovation status, country and "about me" data
Main Scenario	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user accesses the online application and fills in required information: country, evaluation criteria, and "about me" section 2. The user selects the programmes he/she is interested in 3. The application presents the most suitable 'Financial' programmes

Use Case	Search for 'Partners' programmes (UC2)
Description	The user wants to search for 'Partners' programmes in Europe that could help him/her improving the business/idea he/she is working on
Actors	User, Main Database
Assumptions	The user has evaluated himself or herself according to six criteria defined in the tool: Idea Stage, Technology Maturity, Market maturity, Financials, Amount, Team
Pre-conditions	The database has data from the country selected by the user
Post-conditions	The database stores new, anonymous information about the user: innovation status, country and "about me" data
Main Scenario	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user accesses the online application and fills in required information: country, evaluation criteria, and "about me" section 2. The user selects the programmes he/she is interested in 3. The application presents the most suitable 'Partners' programmes

Use Case	Search for 'Other' programmes (UC3)
Description	The user wants to search for programmes supporting 'Other' needs in Europe that could help him/her improving the business/idea he/she is working on
Actors	User, Main Database
Assumptions	The user has evaluated himself or herself according to six criteria defined in the tool: Idea Stage, Technology Maturity, Market maturity, Financials, Amount, Team
Pre-conditions	The database has data from the country selected by the user
Post-conditions	The database stores new, anonymous information about the user: innovation status, country and "about me" data
Main Scenario	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user accesses the online application and fills in required information: country, evaluation criteria, and "about me" section 2. The user selects the programmes he/she is interested in 3. The application presents the most suitable programmes supporting 'Other' needs

Use Case	Suggest new programmes (UC4)
Description	The user, normally in this case a delegate from a entity with entrepreneurship-related programmes, wants to suggest a new programme to be added to the database of available programmes of the application
Actors	User
Assumptions	The user knows all the information regarding the target programme, and the user has a valid e-mail address
Pre-conditions	The programme is not stored on the database yet
Post-conditions	None
Main Scenario	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user knows a programme not currently stored in the application database 2. The selects the action to send MERLIN an e-mail with the details of the programme 3. MERLIN partners validate the proposal and add it to the database

Use Case	Gather feedback and advice (UC5)
Description	The user wants to have some feedback and advice of next steps to take from the application, given his/her current stage
Actors	User
Assumptions	The user has evaluated himself or herself according to the six criteria defined in the tool: Idea Stage, Technology Maturity, Market Maturity, Financials, Amount, Team
Pre-conditions	The database has data from at least 40 participants in Europe and at least 10 participants from the participant's country
Post-conditions	The database stores new, anonymous information about the user: innovation status, country and "about me" data
Main Scenario	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user accesses the online application and fills in the required information: country, evaluation criteria and "about me" section 2. The user clicks the "Get feedback" button 3. The application presents a report on his/her current status and some advice regarding next actions required to improve

Use Case	Compare to other users (UC6)
Description	The user wants to compare the status of his/her innovation with previous users of the application, either of the same country or in Europe in general
Actors	User, Main Database
Assumptions	The user has evaluated himself or herself according to six criteria defined in the tool: Idea Stage, Technology Maturity, Market Maturity, Financials, Amount, Team
Pre-conditions	The database has data from at least 40 participants in Europe and at least 10 participants from the participant country
Post-conditions	The database stores new, anonymous information about the user: innovation status, country and "about me" data
Main Scenario	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The user accesses the online application and fills in required information: country, evaluation criteria and "about me" section 2. The user clicks the "Compare" button 3. The application presents a graphical report on his/her current status with respect to the status of already available data

Use Case	Add new programme (UC7)
Description	A developer has to add a new programme to the database
Actors	Developer, Main Database
Assumptions	Developer has the rights to access and modify the application
Pre-conditions	The programme does exist and is not in the database. It should be added to the application and made available to users
Post-conditions	The programme has been added
Main Scenario	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The developer accesses the online platform and identifies himself or herself 2. The developers add the new programme and sets its characteristics: country, type of programme, and values for the six criteria (Idea Stage, Technology Maturity, Market Maturity, Financials, Amount, Team)

Use Case	Update application features (UC8)
Description	The application has to be modified in order to add new feature or change sorting algorithms
Actors	Developer, Main Database
Assumptions	Developer has the rights to access and modify the application
Pre-conditions	None
Post-conditions	The new functionality has been added to the application
Main Scenario	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The developer accesses the online platform and identifies himself or herself 2. The developers add the new features by modifying appropriate files or by adding new ones

Use Case	Check usage statistics (UC9)
Description	Developers want to check the current statistics of users of the platform
Actors	Developer, Main Database
Assumptions	Developer has the rights to access the application
Pre-conditions	None
Post-conditions	None
Main Scenario	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The developer accesses the online platform and identifies himself or herself 2. The developers checks the available data and download in a format (like CSV or EXCEL) suitable for further processing

3.4. Traceability from functional requirements to use cases

The next step is to establish the link between requirements and use cases, in order to detect possible deficiencies, functional requirements not involved in any use case or vice versa. This would be a sign of incompleteness in any of the two groups. The following Table shows the correspondences between the functional requirements and the use cases identified. The mapping shows that all the functional requirements are considered through the use cases. Non-functional requirements express general requirements about the application that are not directly related to its functionality, such as maintainability, security, performance, etc. As such, they permeate the entire application and, therefore, they are related to all use cases.

Functional requirement	Use Case/s
FR1	UC1 - UC3
FR2	UC1 - UC3
FR3	UC1 - UC3
FR4	UC1 - UC3, UC5, UC6, UC9

Functional Requirement	Use Case/s
FR5	UC4, UC7
FR6	UC1 - UC3, UC8
FR7	UC1 - UC3
FR8	UC1 - UC3

3.5. Application Architecture

Given the previous list of requirements and use cases needed to implement the online application, the next step is to define a first version of the architecture that allows us to cope with all the desired functionality. The architecture for the online application, obtained when considering the previous requirements, is shown in Figure 2. As can be seen, it is the typical architecture of a web application with database, where clients are web browsers that download the application from a web server, which is connected to a database to store/load data for managing the application.

Figure 2. Client – server architecture with web clients

3.6. Modelling the graphical user interface

The design of the graphical interface and the interaction with the user has been firstly defined by using the *Interaction Flow Modeling Language (IFML)*^{9,10}. IFML is a standard modelling language, which objective is to allow tools to generate graphical implementations of the graphical models in different target infrastructures and languages (desktop, mobile, web, Java, .NET, etc.). In this case, IFML will be used only as a modelling language for defining the application, which will be later on implemented. Figure 3 shows the diagram that models the application.

As can be seen in the figure, it comprises two views, ‘*Programme selection view*’ and ‘*Results view*’, connected by a button, ‘*Search programmes*’, which triggers the transition between them. This button is only activated once the user has selected a country, at least one supporting programme, at least one criteria, and has filled in the “About me” section. The ‘*Programme selection view*’ present the user interface for gathering information from the tool user, while the ‘*Results view*’ shows the sorted list of supporting results according to the user input. Some screenshots of the tool are shown at the end of this section, Figure 4 to Figure 10.

⁹ The standard Interaction Flow Modeling Language (IFML), Object Management Group, 2015. <https://www.ifml.org/>

¹⁰ Interaction Flow Modeling Language: Model-Driven UI Engineering of Web and Mobile Apps with IFML. Marco Brambilla, Piero Fraternali. Ed. Morgan Kaufmann. 2014.

Figure 3. IFML model of the two views comprising the online tool

4. Implementation of the online application

Once the requirements, general architecture, and graphical user interface of the online application were decided, the next step is to decide the concrete technologies that will be employed to implement each of the systems comprising the architecture of the application. Given the popularity of web applications, the number of options and technologies available to implement it is huge, but we basically narrowed them down to two main options:

- 1) Implementation inside the Wordpress server that hosts MERLIN webpage. Wordpress is a free and open-source content management system which is highly configurable and extensible thanks to a plugin architecture that allows developers to include new functionality as needed.
- 2) Implementation in a new, dedicated server. In this case, there are two new options: develop a purely server-side approach, like most web pages and applications, or develop a client-side application, what is called a Single-Page Application.

The decision between these options does not affect the functionality of the tool, or at least we think it won't, but rather the required infrastructure to be employed and the expertise demanded from the developers. At first sight, it seems that integrating the web application inside the infrastructure already available, that is, inside MERLIN Wordpress, is the best option from both a budget and time-to-deployment point of view. However, given the difficulty to create and integrate a plugin in Wordpress, and the need to keep it updated, since Wordpress is one of the most cyber-attacked applications worldwide, we decided to abandon this option. Besides, we didn't want to insert any element that could destabilize MERLIN webpage while the application was being developed.

Thus, we decided to implement the application on its own server as a **Single-Page Application (SPA)** due to their advantages over server-side ones. SPAs are web applications in which the page is dynamically modified by the application itself, but without loading or reloading any new page from the server. All the resources needed to display and control the application, that is, pages (HTML), styles (CSS) and code (Javascript), are loaded the first time, and then the application logic dynamically modifies the content as it interacts with the user, loading/storing new data, mostly from databases, as needed. This way, applications behave more like desktop applications and the flickering effect observed in traditional web sites, when switching from one page to another, is eliminated.

Another very important feature of SPAs is that the computation is performed on the client-side rather than on the server-side, which brings two additional advantages to this approach: (i) servers can now become mere file servers and perform less computation, which means less expensive servers; and (ii) communication with the server can be dramatically reduced, which means that a lower bandwidth can be contracted, which means again less expensive servers, as well as less network traffic and congestion. However, no approach is perfect, and the main drawbacks of SPAs are:

- Longer loading times, since main resources are loaded from the beginning of the application execution. It can be problematic at some points and in some locations, but nowadays network bandwidth is getting better and better and is, in general, not a limitation.
- SEO (Search Engine Optimization) positioning. This is the real problem of SPAs, since they rely on content dynamically generated by Javascript. And web crawlers do not normally parse or execute Javascript. This means that many of the SPA content will never be indexed by search engines. This is

however changing, as more search engines are getting aware of the existence of SPAs, and are updating web crawlers to index their content.

- Javascript has to be enabled on the web browser, and thus the devices used to access the application have to be correctly configured and have enough computation power to execute it. But nowadays devices are more and more powerful, and we don't see this fact as a limitation of the approach.

Regarding the concrete technologies available for implementing SPAs, among the available frameworks is worth highlighting Angular (developed by Google), Ember.js (employed in websites like LinkedIn or Twitch.tv), Meteor.js (a complete solution for front-end and back-end), Vue.js (developed by former Google programmers) and React (maintained by Facebook), to mention a few. Angular was selected among them as the target implementation framework for the application since UPCT already had experience developing SPA with it. More details about Angular and its use in the application are provided in section 4.2.

For the server and database, we decided to try to use a “database-free” approach thanks to the features provided by Angular. After some testing, we checked that it was feasible to store the database of supporting programmes as JSON files, one per country, and use Angular *\$http* service to download it dynamically from the server once needed. For storing data from the user, regarding the status of his/her innovation (Idea Stage, Technology Maturity, Market Maturity, Financials, Amount, Team), country, “about me” data, and programmes he/she is interested in, a Google Form stored in MERLIN shared folder was configured and successfully used, thanks to the API provided. This way, the application needs a simple file server to store the files comprising it (HTML pages, CSS styles, Javascript source files, images, and JSON data-sets).

4.1. Recommendation algorithm

Based on the questions of the participant background questionnaire described in section 2 of this deliverable, we decided to classify supporting programmes according to the same criteria and define a couple of recommendation algorithms to filter them and present the results back to the user. Although the title of the subsections mentions “recommendation”, the tool does not employ a recommendation algorithm, like the ones found in Amazon for instance. Those algorithms try to recommend you new items based on your preferences, the rating you provide to similar items, and the ratings other users with whom you share items and preferences have given to items you haven't still rated.

In this case, we could say that the algorithms are “matching” algorithms, in the sense that they try to find the best match between the values provided by the user for the six criteria, and the values for those same criteria available on the database. It was important to provide a “score” to the selected programmes to present a sorted list to the user, with the programmes most suitable for him/her, given the status of the innovation, appearing first. In this case, the score value is treated as a “distance” value, meaning that, the higher the value, the less suitable the programme is for the user, since the values of the programme criteria are further away than the values for the criteria provided by the user. Thus, the ordering is from lower value to higher value.

Regarding non-available values, it was decided that they were going to be ignored in both cases (the user or the programme didn't provide them). With these ideas in mind, two filtering and sorting algorithms were defined and added to the online application, so that users could select between them (see Figure 5, below the map).

4.1.1 Strict algorithm

This algorithm filters out some of the programmes stored on the database given the current status of the user and the following rules: if any of the criteria of the programme exceeds in more than 1 unit the value of the user for that same criteria, then the programme is filtered-out and not shown to the user. We assume that the user is below the expectations of the programme and thus, it is not a good option for him/her. This difference of 1 provides flexibility when selecting programs and takes into account the subjective difference when setting the values of the criteria: in the case of the MERLIN partners, when they classify the programs and, in the case of the user, when he evaluates himself. In this way, we try to compensate for the subjectivity in the selection of the values of the criteria.

As we have mentioned above, we ignore any criteria not present in both the user and programme values. In case none of the criteria provided appear on a given programme, such programme is not filtered out but rather presented at the end of the sort list (it is given the ‘Infinity’ value).

If all the values for all criteria of the intersection user-programme are higher for the user, then we compute the score as:

$$\sum_{i \in \{UC \cap PC\}} 10^{(UC_i - PC_i)} \quad \text{where: } UC_i \text{ is the value of the } i\text{-th common } User \text{ Criteria}$$

PC_i is the value of the *Programme* i -th common *Criteria*

We use an exponential score, based on the distance between the user and programme values, instead of a linear one, to reflect the fact that a difference of 2 in one criteria is “worst” than having two criteria with a difference of just 1. In the first case, the programme will have a value of 100, while in the second one it will be 20, and thus the second programme will appear before the first one.

4.1.2 Soft algorithm

This algorithm does not filter any programme out, but rather sorts them according to user status, and presents the results ordered by a “score” criteria calculated in a similar way as the previous algorithm. In this case, the score value is calculated by applying the absolute value to the difference between the values of the common criteria, as shown in the following equation:

$$\sum_{i \in \{UC \cap PC\}} 10^{|UC_i - PC_i|} \quad \text{where: } UC_i \text{ is the value of the } i\text{-th common } User \text{ Criteria}$$

PC_i is the value of the *Programme* i -th common *Criteria*

Thus, this algorithm is even more permissive with the difference of criteria values between programmes (established by MERLIN partners) and users (guessed by themselves). Although we tried to make this evaluation as easy as possible, providing examples for each of the values of each criteria, there is still plenty of subjectivity in both the consortium partners and the application users when selecting values.

On the other hand, the results obtained may not be as reliable as the ones provided by the ‘Strict’ algorithm, since for users who over-estimate their own status, this algorithm may suggest programmes that are above their real capabilities and status. But, if the user under-estimates his/her status, then this algorithm will show results that were filtered out by the ‘Strict’ algorithm, and which may be suitable for him/her.

4.2. Design of the application user interface with Angular

Angular¹¹ was initially developed by Google in 2010 as a multi-platform open-source framework, with MIT license, to develop SPAs following a variant of Model-View-Controller (MVC)¹² architectural pattern entitled Model-View-ViewModel. MVC pattern and its variants are the most used ones in the design of applications that have a graphical interface. In this pattern, the *Model* has the data, shown to the user by the *View*. The *Controller* mediates between them and the user, making changes to the *View* if the *Model* is changed. In Angular, HTML pages and CSS styles play the *View* role, while Javascript is the *ViewModel*, which keeps a bidirectional relationship between the *Model* (the data) and the *View*.

The implementation of the application relies also on the Bootstrap¹³ library, one of the most, if not the most, used libraries for managing the look and feel of webpages. Released as a free and open-source framework for the front-end, it was originally developed exclusively for Twitter, and made available to the public in 2011. With all this information, and the IFML diagram modelling the graphical shown in Figure 3, the Angular application was developed comprising two views (HTML files) and two controllers (Javascript files), the main `index.html` file, and the configuration file for loading resources and configuring some parameters of the Angular application.

An SVG (*Scalable Vector Graphic*) version of the EU-28 map was integrated in the web application to allow the user to select the country he/she is interested in (see Figure 5). Being a vector graphic, the map supports zoom-in and zoom-out operations without losing quality. Besides, all countries are individually identified, classified and labelled. This makes it very easy to introduce modifications in the map as needed. For the results view (see Figure 10), the following graphical icons have been used to represent the suitability score of each of the six criteria, and the overall suitability of each programme. We decided to use graphical values because we did not want to provide current values (which, on the other hand, may mean nothing to the user) and because graphics are an easier way to express fuzzy information.

Graphical representations of the suitability values of each criteria		
Non-common criteria	Suitability values (lower to higher)	Criteria difference too high

¹¹ Angular homepage, <https://angular.io/>

¹² The evolution of graphical user interface architectures. Martin Fowler. <https://martinfowler.com/eaDev/uiArchs.html>

¹³ Bootstrap homepage, <https://getbootstrap.com/>

Overall graphical values for a programme	
Overall suitability value (from higher to lower value)	Not enough data to recommend programme

4.3. Database of EU-28 programmes

As mentioned above, the database of EU-28 programmes is stored in JSON files. In order to reduce required bandwidth and computation power on client devices, 29 files have been created to store the programmes available: one per country and one for EU programmes. Once the user selects a country in the application, only that file and the EU file are retrieved from the server. For each programme, the following information is stored:

- Name, website, region and programme scope (Regional, National or International).
- Type of programme (Financial, Partners or Other), and further details about the programme. These further details depend on the type of programme, and the following values are available:

Financial	Partners	Other
Public Funding to develop innovation further	Potential co-founders	Support in developing a successful business model
Public funding to reach market	Technology development partners	Support developing a go-to-market strategy
Public funding to grow	Market development partners	Introductions to potential clients
Low-interest business loans	Technology platform partners	Intellectual property advice
Tailored bank-loans	Distribution partners	Access to specialist equipment
Angel Investment (<€100,000)	Corporate piloting partners	Access to workspace
Seed Investment (<€500,000)	Incubation/acceleration programmes	
VC Investment (>€1m)		

- Values for the six criteria: Idea Stage, Technology Maturity, Market Maturity, Financials, Amount and Team.
- Constraints that may be important for the users of the tool when deciding whether to apply for it.

- Which kind of EU funds they depend on (if any): EFSI, ERDF, EIC, HORIZON 2020, EaSI, EIB, InnovFin, EIF, FEDER.

These values are stored in JSON files for each programme. As mentioned in the introduction, currently (November 2018), only values for programmes in Spain and Ireland are currently available, since those countries were selected for the first stage. But MERLIN partners will add new countries and programmes over the course of the project. A sample data of one of the programmes available in Ireland, in JSON format, is shown below:

```
{
  "Name": "Local Enterprise Office",
  "Website": "https://www.localenterprise.ie/About-Us/Services/",
  "Country": "Ireland",
  "Region": "All",
  "Scope": "Regional",
  "Level 1": "Financial",
  "Level 2.1": "Public funding to grow",
  "Level 2.2": "Public funding to reach market",
  "Idea Stage": 2,
  "Technology Maturity": 2,
  "Market Maturity": 3,
  "Financials": 3,
  "Amount": 5,
  "Team": 2,
  "Constraints": "<10 employees",
  "EFSI": "",
  "ERDF": "",
  "EIC": "",
  "HORIZON 2020": "",
  "EaSI": "",
  "EIB": "",
  "InnovFin": "",
  "EIF": "",
  "FEDER": ""
}
```

Besides, JSON format is very easy to edit and extend. There are many libraries available to process it in many programming languages, and can be easily integrated with other tools.

4.4. Screenshots of the tool

This section presents some screenshots of the tool, presented in the same order as the user will see them in the online tool, which corresponds to the following views:

- 1) **Programme selection view:** description of the tool and purpose, as well as some general instructions on how to use it (Figure 4); country and sorting algorithm selection (Figure 5); type of supporting programmes the user is looking for (Figure 6); buttons for selecting the values for each of the six criteria (Figure 7); section where the user has to provide data “about me” for helping MERLIN perform further analysis (Figure 8).
- 2) **Results view:** description of the results obtained, legend of the graphical values and some considerations the user has to be aware of on how the programmes have been selected and ordered (Figure 9); table showing the programmes selected according to user needs and user status, ordered according to a score value (Figure 10).

Figure 4. Summary of the purpose and usage of the online tool

Figure 5. Selection of country and sorting algorithm

Figure 6. Kind of programme user is looking for

Please select your current status regarding *Idea Stage*

0	1	2	3	4	5
N/A	I have ideas that I believe to have commercial potential	I have an idea for the commercialisation of my results	I have developed potential Business Model(s)	I am actively exploring the potential business models	I have a proven business model and am focusing on getting to market

Please select your current status regarding *Technology Maturity*

0	1	2	3	4	5
N/A	Technology has been validated in a lab environment - basic components	Technology has been validated in a relevant environment - model system	Technology has been demonstrated in a relevant environment - prototype system	System prototype demonstrated in a operational environment - beta test	System complete and qualified - ready to ship

Figure 7. User input regarding his/her status (only two of the six criteria are shown)

About me:

Role:

Sector:

Organization:

- ✓ University
- Research Centre
- Corporate
- Technical SME
- Non technical SME
- Startup
- Other

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 780460
 @Merlin_ICT

Figure 8. General data about user to help us analyse who is using the tool and his/her current status

METHODOLOGIES FOR RESEARCH LED INNOVATION

The tables below show the results of the search in the database of programmes with the following criteria:

Technology Maturity: 2 **Market Maturity: 3** **Financials: 2** **Amount: 1**

The results are sorted according to score and suitability, taking into account the criteria appearing *both in the programmes and the ones selected by the user*. There is a graphical visual overall score at the beginning of each row summarising the score. Full circle means 'perfect match', and from there, the bigger the pie section, the higher the matching score is. If there are no common criteria between programmes and user selection, a warning icon appears (meaning that there is not enough information). These programmes appear at the end of the tables. Since the scores are computed taking into account the criteria appearing in both (user selection and programmes), it is possible that a programme with just one common criteria appears before others with more common ones. To avoid this false impression, graphical values are also provided for individual matching criteria (solid star, half star, hollow star and forbidden sign if values are too far away from each other). The horizontal bar means 'not matching'.

Figure 9. Description of the way to interpret the results view

PROGRAMMES FOCUSING ON 'PARTNERS'

Overall	Name	Region	Scope	Level 2.1	Level 2.2	Constraints	d_Idea Stage	d_Technology Maturity	d_Market Maturity	d_Financials	d_Amount	d_Team
	Innovation Vouchers	All	National	Technology development partners	Market development partners	Agricultural Sector	—	—	—	—	★	—
	Arclabs	Waterford & Kilkenny	Regional	Incubation/acceleration programmes	Access to specialist equipment		—	—	—	★	—	—
	Yieldlab	Dublin, Galway, London & St Louis	National	Incubation/acceleration programmes		Only Agrifood technology companies	—	—	—	—	☆	—
	DIT Hothouse	Dublin	Regional	Incubation/acceleration programmes		Only researchers in Dublin Institute of Technology	—	—	★	—	⊖	—
	Dogpatch Labs	Dublin	Regional	Incubation/acceleration programmes			—	—	—	—	—	—

Figure 10. Sorted list with the results with a graphical scale

5. Conclusions and future enhancements

This deliverable has described the design of the questionnaire and an online tool to help users find the most suitable supporting programmes in Europe, according to the user needs. The purpose of this questionnaire, entitled “Participant Background Questionnaire” (PBQ), is to identify at what stage the participant is at in the innovation from initial idea to market introduction as well as capturing what type of support services they are most interested in. The PBQ has been provided to all participants of MERLIN activities in order to gather their current status.

The design of the online tool is based on well-known, software engineering methodologies. We started from the requirements phase, went through the design of the application architecture and its graphical interface, and finished with its detailed implementation using the Angular framework. The tool includes the questions appearing in the PBQ as a way to assess the current status of the user and suggest supporting programmes in the chosen EU country. The tool is hosted in a subdomain of the project website: <https://growthradar.merlin-ict.eu> and it is available to the general public. By the time this deliverable was published (November 2018), its database stored programmes from Ireland and Spain mainly, since these two countries were chosen for the first version of the tool. But all the partners of MERLIN consortium will complete the database with the programmes available on their countries and countries nearby during the project lifecycle. Also, any errors found in the database or in the tool itself will be corrected.

Regarding future enhancements, some features were not implemented in this first version of the tool, and MERLIN partners have suggested some improvements while it was being designed. A short and incomplete list of improvements for the next versions of the tool are the following:

- Add the countries that are still not present in the database.
- Add an option to save results as a PDF or CSV file.
- Add scroll to the EU map, since small countries may be difficult to select.
- Provide other ordering criteria to the results, not just overall programme score. For instance, by any of the six criteria.
- Implement the feedback and advice functionality for users.
- Implement the functionality to compare with other participants.

Annex 1. Initial Questionnaire results

Key

N°	Idea	Technology	Market	Financials	Amount	Team
0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
1	I have ideas that I believe to have commercial potential	Technology has been validated in a lab environment - basic components	I have a general idea of relevant sectors/markets	I am exploring how to fund development	€0-10,000	I am currently working on my own
2	I have an idea for the commercialisation of my results	Technology has been validated in a relevant environment - model system	I have a clearly defined market	I have received initial funding from my organisation	€10-35,000	I have general co-developers/co-founders
3	I have developed potential Business Model(s)	Technology has been demonstrated in a relevant environment - prototype system	I have clearly defined market segments and potential customers	I have received initial external funding to develop the idea (private/public)	€35-50,000	I have developers/co-founders and an initial team of employees
4	I am actively exploring the potential business models	System prototype demonstrated in a operational environment - beta test	I have engaged with potential customers and received inputs	I have received initial investment to develop a prototype	€50-100,000	I have co-founders and an initial team of employees (<5)
5	I have a proven business model and am focusing on getting to market	System complete and qualified - ready to ship	I have developed pilots or trials with potential customers	I have received investment to reach the market	€ >100,000	I have co-founders and a team of employees (>5)

Average maturity by city or conference

City/Conference	Idea Stage	Technology Maturity	Market	Financials	Amount Received	Team Details
Cambridge	2,5	2,1	2,4	1,7	1,8	2,3
ECSA	2,3	1,3	1,5	2,3	0,5	2,3
IoT Week	1,0	2,0	1,5	2,0	1,0	1,0
Madrid	1,8	1,5	1,7	1,6	1,5	2,0
Poznan	2,6	2,0	2,8	1,3	0,7	2,4
Vilnius	2,6	3,2	2,6	2,0	2,9	2,2
Warsaw	3,5	3,0	3,1	2,4	2,1	3,4
Total	2,6	2,4	2,5	1,8	1,9	2,4

Average Innovation Maturity by workshop

Workshop	Idea Stage	Technology Maturity	Market	Financials	Amount Received	Team Details
BMC	2,4	2,4	2,5	1,4	2,0	2,2
CDIS	2,8	2,5	2,6	2,1	1,8	2,7
CONF	1,8	1,5	1,5	2,2	0,7	1,8
LSM	2,6	2,2	2,4	1,8	1,9	2,5
Total	2,6	2,4	2,5	1,8	1,9	2,4

Most selected support services by city or conference

	CA M	ECS A	IoT Week	MA D	PO Z	VI L	WA R	Total
Public Funding to develop innovation further	16	3	1	15	13	7	15	70
Public funding to reach market	15	1	1	6	9	7	6	45
Public funding to grow	13	1		3	8	7	11	43
Low-interest business loans	4			2	8	3	2	19
Tailored bank-loans				1	3		1	5
Potential co-founders	7		1	5	5	2	2	22
Technology development partners	13	1	1	10	13	9	5	52
Market development partners	12	1		5	9	6	7	40
Technology platform partners	7	1		5	13	5	6	37
Disribution partners	8	1		2	10	6	13	40
Corporate piloting pilots	6		1		7	4	9	27
Incubation/acceleration programmes	13	3		3	4	9	10	42
Support in developing a successful business model	19	3	1	9	10	10	11	63
Support developing a go-to-market strategy	18		1	6	13		11	49
Introductions to potential clients	21	2		6	13		14	56
Intellectual Property advice	10	2		8	12		5	37
Access to specialist equipment	3			3	7		1	14
Access to workspace	9	1		2	8		4	24
Other (Please write)	2						2	4

Comparison of most demanded service by stage of maturity

Idea

	IDEA STAGE						Total
	0	1	2	3	4	5	
Public Funding to develop innovation further	6	18	17	6	16	7	70
Public funding to reach market	1	12	11	5	11	5	45
Public funding to grow		9	9	5	14	6	43
Low-interest business loans	2	3	4	1	7	2	19
Tailored bank-loans	1		2		1	1	5
Angel Investment (<€100,000)	2	7	12	4	12	4	41
Seed Investment (<€500,000)	1	8	10	3	7	4	33
Potential co-founders	4	6	4	4	1	3	22
Technology development partners	5	11	13	6	12	5	52
Market development partners	2	9	10	3	13	3	40
Technology platform partners	4	5	7	8	10	3	37
Disribution partners	2	3	9	6	18	2	40
Corporate piloting pilots	1	6	7	2	9	2	27
Incubation/acceleration programmes	1	10	14	6	8	3	42
Support in developing a successful business model	3	16	14	7	17	6	63
Support developing a go-to-market strategy	1	7	13	8	14	6	49
Introductions to potential clients	2	7	11	10	19	7	56
Intellectual Property advice	4	7	11	6	6	3	37
Access to specialist equipment	2	7	3		1	1	14
Access to workspace	2	2	7	6	5	2	24
Other (Please write)		1	1	2			4

Technology

TECHNOLOGY READINESS							
	0	1	2	3	4	5	Total
Public Funding to develop innovation further	12	17	13	15	8	5	70
Public funding to reach market	6	8	11	12	5	3	45
Public funding to grow	3	8	9	8	8	7	43
Low-interest business loans	5	2	4	2	3	3	19
Tailored bank-loans	2	1	1		1		5
Angel Investment (<€100,000)	4	10	7	9	7	4	41
Seed Investment (<€500,000)	3	8	9	5	4	4	33
Potential co-founders	6	8	3	3	1	1	22
Technology development partners	9	15	6	13	5	4	52
Market development partners	3	9	8	8	7	5	40
Technology platform partners	6	8	6	8	5	4	37
Disribution partners	4	7	9	6	8	6	40
Corporate piloting pilots	4	5	6	7	3	2	27
Incubation/acceleration programmes	5	11	14	6	5	1	42
Support in developing a successful business model	7	14	13	7	12	10	63
Support developing a go-to-market strategy	6	8	11	8	8	8	49
Introductions to potential clients	10	11	11	6	8	10	56
Intellectual Property advice	5	8	11	6	3	4	37
Access to specialist equipment	5	4	1	2		2	14
Access to workspace	5	6	4	3	4	2	24
Other (Please write)	1	2	1				4

Market

MARKET DEVELOPMENT							
	0	1	2	3	4	5	Total
Public Funding to develop innovation further	7	20	15	15	6	7	70
Public funding to reach market	1	12	10	13	7	2	45
Public funding to grow		10	13	9	7	4	43
Low-interest business loans	1	5	2	8	2	1	19
Tailored bank-loans	1	1		3			5
Angel Investment (<€100,000)	1	12	7	11	7	3	41
Seed Investment (<€500,000)	1	7	10	7	5	3	33
Potential co-founders	3	8	5	3	2	1	22
Technology development partners	4	19	7	13	5	4	52
Market development partners	1	12	9	13	3	2	40
Technology platform partners	3	9	4	13	5	3	37
Disribution partners		7	5	14	9	5	40
Corporate piloting pilots		9	6	7	5		27
Incubation/acceleration programmes	1	10	11	9	9	2	42
Support in developing a successful business model	3	19	12	11	11	7	63
Support developing a go-to-market strategy	1	14	4	13	9	8	49
Introductions to potential clients	2	10	5	15	16	8	56
Intellectual Property advice	2	11	5	11	5	3	37
Access to specialist equipment	2	6	1	4	1		14
Access to workspace	2	5	2	7	5	3	24
Other (Please write)		1		1	2		4

Financials

FINANCE RECEIVED							
	0	1	2	3	4	5	Total
Public Funding to develop innovation further	8	33	9	10	6	4	70
Public funding to reach market	4	23	7	8	2	1	45
Public funding to grow	2	17	7	10	5	2	43
Low-interest business loans	2	7	3	5	2		19
Tailored bank-loans	1	2		2			5
Angel Investment (<€100,000)	1	21	8	8	2	1	41
Seed Investment (<€500,000)	1	17	5	6	3	1	33
Potential co-founders	5	11	2	3	1		22
Technology development partners	3	29	6	8	5	1	52
Market development partners	1	19	5	8	6	1	40
Technology platform partners	3	18	4	5	6	1	37
Disribution partners	3	14	8	8	5	2	40
Corporate piloting pilots	2	13	3	5	4		27
Incubation/acceleration programmes	4	22	6	5	4	1	42
Support in developing a successful business model	7	29	8	10	7	2	63
Support developing a go-to-market strategy	6	26	6	6	4	1	49
Introductions to potential clients	6	30	5	5	6	4	56
Intellectual Property advice	3	20	2	8	3	1	37
Access to specialist equipment	2	9	1	2			14
Access to workspace	4	13	3	3		1	24
Other (Please write)		2	1	1			4

AMOUNT RECEIVED							
	0	1	2	3	4	5	Total
Public Funding to develop innovation further	27	23	1	6	4	9	70
Public funding to reach market	13	22	2	4	1	3	45
Public funding to grow	13	15	1	5	4	5	43
Low-interest business loans	6	8			3	2	19
Tailored bank-loans	2	3					5
Angel Investment (<€100,000)	7	22	1	4	3	4	41
Seed Investment (<€500,000)	11	10	1	4	2	5	33
Potential co-founders	9	10		2		1	22
Technology development partners	19	20	2	7	1	3	52
Market development partners	10	18	1	4	1	6	40
Technology platform partners	14	10	2	4	4	3	37
Disribution partners	11	12	1	2	7	7	40
Corporate piloting pilots	10	9	1	4	2	1	27
Incubation/acceleration programmes	17	15		3	2	5	42
Support in developing a successful business model	24	23		3	5	8	63
Support developing a go-to-market strategy	15	23	1		4	6	49
Introductions to potential clients	20	20	1		7	8	56
Intellectual Property advice	12	15	2	2	2	4	37
Access to specialist equipment	8	4		1		1	14
Access to workspace	9	10		1	3	1	24
Other (Please write)	1	1			2		4

Team

TEAM							
	0	1	2	3	4	5	Total
Public Funding to develop innovation further	9	7	25	16	5	8	70
Public funding to reach market	2	7	14	15	5	2	45
Public funding to grow		5	15	13	6	4	43
Low-interest business loans	1	3	5	6	1	3	19
Tailored bank-loans	1	1	1	2			5
Angel Investment (<€100,000)	2	6	14	12	4	3	41
Seed Investment (<€500,000)	2	4	11	9	6	1	33
Potential co-founders	5	6	7	3		1	22
Technology development partners	5	9	19	14	2	3	52
Market development partners	1	4	15	11	6	3	40
Technology platform partners	3	5	8	8	7	6	37
Disribution partners		3	10	10	8	9	40
Corporate piloting pilots	1	2	9	7	5	3	27
Incubation/acceleration programmes	1	8	16	10	5	2	42
Support in developing a successful business model	5	11	15	14	8	10	63
Support developing a go-to-market strategy	2	5	16	12	5	9	49
Introductions to potential clients	2	8	15	14	5	12	56
Intellectual Property advice	2	4	17	10	2	2	37
Access to specialist equipment	2		8	3		1	14
Access to workspace	2	4	9	4	1	4	24
Other (Please write)		1	1			2	4

